

singleton and twin IVF pregnancies were identified by matching two databases: the ATTIKON Assisted Reproduction Unit Database and the Maternity Databank. The general obstetric population delivering singletons and twins during the same period of time served as controls. Outcomes were compared separately for singleton and twin pregnancies. RESULTS: 99 women who delivered after conceiving with IVF treatment were studied. 1231 women who delivered in the same period and had conceived spontaneously served as controls. IVF women were older, [mean (SD) age: 34.8 (5.1) years versus 29.0(6.4) years ($P<0.01$) in singleton and 33.6(3.1) years versus 28.4(4.4) years in twin pregnancies ($P<0.01$)] and more likely to be primiparous (64.7% versus 37.4% in singleton, and 54% versus 40.4% in twin pregnancies, $p < 0.01$). After adjusting for age and parity women with IVF singleton pregnancies had a higher incidence of antenatal vaginal bleeding, placenta praevia ($P < 0.05$) and preeclampsia. Obstetric outcomes in IVF twin pregnancies were comparable to those encountered by spontaneous twins. CONCLUSIONS: Women carrying singletons following IVF treatment are at greater risk of antepartum bleeding. Conception by IVF does not expose twin pregnancies to any additional risks over and above those already present in naturally conceived twins.

P106

THE FREQUENCY AND RISK FACTORS RELATED TO INTRA UTERINE FETAL DEATH

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Back ground : Intra uterine fetal death (IUFD) is a traumatic event for the family which occurs in for about 1% of all pregnancyies. in comparison With other countries this rate is increasing. Certainly many factor causes (IUFD) as intra uterine infection, lethal malformations, fetal growth retardation and abruption placenta. Material and method This research was a case –control study to determine risk factors for (IUFD) . We use a standard questionnaire was designed of maternal and fetal factors. The questionnaire was filld by using medical records between 2001-2006 in teaching hospital imam Ahwaz . Samples including 953 records including 358 cases and 595 controls. Result Statistical reports from teaching hospital Amman estimated the rate of IUFD 4%. We found related with high age mother ($p= 0/002$) with race ($p = 0/000$) post IUFD ($p = 0/001$) Malformation ($p= 0/000$) fetal weigh ($p= 0/022$) pregnancy complication ($p=0/025$) and maternal disease ($p= 0/000$) Conclusion : This study show that rate (4%) is increasing in Iran . it is difficult to identify preventable factors of IUFD . How ever consultation proper prenatal care early diagnosis of complications and careful evaluation may reduce the incidence of IUFD.

P107

DIABETES INSIPIDUS AND TWO CONSECUTIVE PREGNANCIES: A CASE REPORT

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We report a case of a woman with a preexisting Diabetes Insipidus (DI), who had two consecutive uncomplicated pregnancies. Both pregnancies resulted after spontaneous conception and had a similar uneventful course. At the time of conception the patient was receiving 1-desamino-8D-arginine-vasopressin (DDAVP) 3 ml/day which maintained an urinary volume of 2-3 liters/day. Pre-existed DI can be handled carefully and result in an uncomplicated pregnancy. In such cases careful monitoring of the patient's fluid balance and liver enzymes, as well as monitoring for pre-eclampsia and oligohydramnios during pregnancy are essential.

P108

SUCCESSFUL PREGNANCY ONE YEAR AFTER TREATMENT WITH RADIOACTIVE IODINE FOR THYROID CANCER: A CASE REPORT

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Introduction: Radioactive iodine (^{131}I) has been used effectively in diagnosis and treatment of thyroid cancers in order to prevent relapses and treat metastases. Since radiation is delivered to the whole body, including ovaries, it's a reasonable